

Stability Indicating Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatographic Assay for the Determination of Udenafil in Bulk

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Abstract

A stability-indicating RP-HPLC method was developed for the quantitative determination of Udenafil in bulk. It involved a Phenomenex C-18 column (250mm × 4.6 mm i.d., 3.5 μm) as stationary phase. The isocratic LC method employs solution A and B as mobile phase. Solution A contains acetonitrile and solution B contains sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate dehydrate buffer in ratio (85:15 v/v) with pH 6.0. The flow rate was 1.0 mL/min and the detection wavelength was 291 nm. The retention time of Udenafil is about 3.0 ± 0.2 min. Udenafil was subjected to different stress conditions prescribed by the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines. The drug was subjected to stress conditions of hydrolysis, oxidation and photolysis degradation. Degradation was found to occur in hydrolytic stress and to some extent in oxidative stress and photolytic conditions. The assay of stress samples was calculated against a qualified reference standard and the percentage degradation in each condition are reported. The developed RP-HPLC method was partially validated with respect to specificity and selectivity, linearity, LOD and LOQ.

Keywords

Udenafil, Stress degradation, RP-HPLC, degradation products, erectile dysfunction

Introduction

Udenafil is chemically 3-(1-methyl-7-oxo-3-propyl-6*H*-pyrazolo[4,3-*d*]pyrimidin-5-yl)-*N*-[2-(1-methylpyrrolidin-2-yl)ethyl]-4-propoxybenzenesulfonamide which is intended for the treatment of erectile dysfunction. It is a benzenesulfonamide derivative with vasodilatory activity. Udenafil selectively inhibits phosphodiesterase type V (PDE V), thus inhibiting the degradation of cyclic guanosine monophosphate (cGMP) found in the smooth muscle of the corpus cavernosa and corpus spongiosum of the penis; inhibition of cGMP degradation results in prolonged muscle relaxation, vasodilation, and blood engorgement of the corpus cavernosa, and, so, prolonged penile erection [1]. Through an extensive literature survey it

was found that very few reported methods are available for the determination and quantification of Udenafil. However Soo Kyung Bae *et. al* (2008) [2] have developed and reported an simple ultra-performance liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry (UPLC/MS/MS) method for the determination of udenafil and its active metabolite, DA-8164, in human plasma and urine using sildenafil as an internal standard (IS). Wan-Sung Ku *et. al* (2011) [3] have developed and reported an analytical method for udenafil in rat plasma by using liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS). B. Siddartha *et. al* (2014) [4] have reported an accurate UV Spectrophotometric method for estimation of udenafil in bulk and tablet dosage form. Wael Abu Dayyih *et. al* (2018) [5] have developed and reported a reversed phase high performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for estimation and determination of two actives pharmaceutical ingredient Udenafil (Zydena) and Dapoxetine (Priligy). In presence of pregabalin as internal standard (IS). Sandesh Bherje *et. al* (2024) [6] have reported a clinical research which affirmed that the combination of Udenafil and Dapoxetine hydrochloride yields greater improvement in erectile dysfunction compared to the use of individual medications. Stress degradation studies have not been reported for Udenafil.

Figure 1: Structure of Udenafil

Experimental

Chemicals and Reagents

Acetonitrile, methanol, ammonium acetate, formic acid, Perchloric acid, sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate dehydrate, 0.1 N sodium hydroxide, 0.1 M hydrochloric acid and 3% hydrogen peroxide were supplied by S.D Fine chemicals. Water from milli-Q RO system was used. Reference standard of Udenafil was obtained as gift sample from Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission (IPC), New Delhi, India

Instrumentation

Shimadzu Prominence HPLC (Tokyo, Japan) system LC-20 AT-VP solvent delivery system with manual 20 μ L loop capacity sample injector, UV detector SPD M-20AVP and Lab solution CS software for data management was used. Phenomenex C-18 column (250mm \times 4.6 mm i.d., 3.5 μ m) was used as the stationary phase, and acetonitrile: Sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate dehydrate buffer in an (85:15 v/v) ratio as the mobile phase with a pH of 6.0

at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min with a detection wavelength of 291 nm.

Preparation of stock Solutions

A standard solution of 1 mg/ml of Udenafil was prepared by dissolving 50 mg of Udenafil in 50 ml of Acetonitrile, labeled and stored the solution in a refrigerator below 8°C.

Stress studies

All the stress decomposition studies were performed at the initial drug concentration of 0.1 mg/mL (100 µg/mL). Acid hydrolysis was performed in 0.1 N HCl at 27 °C for 24 h. The study in basic solution was carried out in 0.1 N NaOH at 27°C for 24 h. For study in neutral solution, drug dissolved in water was kept in room temperature for 24 h. Oxidation studies were carried out at room temperature in 0.3% hydrogen peroxide for 24 h. Photo degradation studies were carried out according to Q1B in ICH guidelines. Samples were exposed to UV light for 24h. Samples were withdrawn at appropriate time and subjected to HPLC analysis.

Results and Discussion

Method Development and Optimization

The main objective was to develop a method for the separation and quantitation of Udenafil in the presence of degradation products. The system suitability specification that provide assistance in achieving this purpose were also calculated. Some of them are theoretical plate number, the injection precision and the tailing factor. The chromatographic separation was achieved by following isocratic program using Acetonitrile: Sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate dehydrate buffer in a ratio of (85:15 v/v) mobile phase with pH 6.0. Detection was carried out with UV detector at detection wavelength 291 nm. The sample injection volume was 10 µL. The retention time of Udenafil is about 3.0 ± 0.2 min and optimized chromatograms is shown in Figure 3.

Method Validation

Specificity and Selectivity

The specificity of the method was established through study of resolution factors of the drug peak from the nearest resolving peak, and also among all other peaks.

Linearity

Linearity test solutions were prepared from stock solution at five concentration levels which are 1 µg/ml, 5 µg/ml, 10 µg/ml, 15 µg/ml and 20 µg/ml. The concentrations ranging from 1 µg/ml to 20 µg/ml for Udenafil was analysed by HPLC. The peak areas were calculated (Table I). The calibration curve was plotted using the peak areas and concentration of the standard solutions (Figure 2). Standard curve fitting is determined by applying the simplest model that adequately describes the concentration-response relationship using appropriate weighing and statistical tests for goodness of fit.

LOD and LOQ

Limit of detection (LOD) is the lowest concentration of analyte in a sample that can be detected, but not necessarily quantitative, under the stated experimental conditions and determined by measuring the signal-to-noise ratio at 3:1. The signal-to-noise ratio was performed by measuring the signal of known low concentrations of drug. Limit of quantification (LOQ) is the lowest concentration of an analyte in a sample that can be determined with precision and accuracy under the stated experimental conditions and determined by measuring the signal-to noise ratio at 10:1. The signal-to-noise ratios was performed by measuring the signal of known low concentrations of drug.

Results from Forced Degradation Studies

Specificity of the method was exhibited by analyzing blank prepared as per test method. These results demonstrate that there was no interference at the retention time of Udenafil from the other excipient compounds and, therefore, confirms the specificity of the method. All degradation products formed under stress conditions were well resolved from analyte peaks (Figure 4 to Figure 8) and thus confirms the stability-indicating power of the developed method.

A summary data of stress study is shown in Table III.

Conclusion

A simple and efficient RP-HPLC stability indicating method was developed and partially validated. This method can be used for the analysis of the drug and the degradation products in stability samples in quality control labs and in industries. The study provides an insight that the drug degrades at all the environments acidic, basic, oxidative and photolytic it becomes vital to further explore the study. The isolation and characterization of the major degradation products can be explored further.

Funding

No funding was provided for this study.

Acknowledgements

All the authors would like to thank Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, JSS College of Pharmacy for providing with the facilities to carry out the research smoothly. We would also like to thank Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission (IPC), New Delhi, India for providing with the reference standard of Udenafil.

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Table I: Linearity and range

S.No	Udenafil concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Peak area for Udenafil (mV)
1	1	9536
2	5	53522
3	10	110472
4	15	167362
5	20	232094

Table II: System suitability parameters

S.No	Parameters	Values obtained for Udenafil
1	Theoretical Plate (N)	2691
2	Linearity range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	1-20
3	Regression equation	$Y = 11654x - 4272.5$
4	Correlation coefficient	0.9991
5	Asymmetry factor	1
6	Tailing factor	0.8
7	LOD (ng/ml)	0.7621
8	LOQ (ng/ml)	2.3095

Table III: Results of forced degradation of Udenafil

Stress conditions	Drug Recovered (%)	Drug Decomposed (%)
Standard drug	100	Not applicable
Acid hydrolysis	63.1	36.9
Basic hydrolysis	76.5	23.5
Neutral	71.2	28.8
Oxidative degradation	74.12	25.8
Photolytic degradation	73.2	26.8

Figure 2: Linearity plot of Udenafil

Figure 3: Optimized HPLC chromatogram of Udenafil standard

Figure 4: Typical HPLC chromatogram of Acid degradation sample with 0.1 M HCl at room temperature

Figure 5: Typical HPLC chromatogram of Base degradation sample with 0.1 M Sodium hydroxide at room temperature

Figure 6: Typical HPLC chromatogram of Neutral degradation sample with water at room temperature

Figure 7: Typical HPLC chromatogram of Oxidative degradation sample with 0.3% Hydrogen peroxide at room temperature

Figure 8: Typical HPLC chromatogram of Photolytic degradation sample at sunlight